

ENTREPRENEURIAL OPENNESS AND OPPORTUNITY RECOGNITION: THE MEDIATING ROLES OF EN- TREPRENEURIAL CONNECTIVITY, VISIBILITY AND CREATIVITY

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PROBLEM STATEMENT

A new venture is a driver for the economy, entrepreneurship is a key driver for economic growth, and entrepreneurs are individuals who pursue opportunities in the marketplace. Bygrave and Hofer (1991) state that it is an essential characteristic of entrepreneurs to perceive an opportunity.

The importance of entrepreneurship in job creation and economic development is acknowledged all over the world. Prospective entrepreneurs (actors) engage in interactions with others, hoping for a role in the opportunities and ventures emerging within. Opportunity discovery consists of actions initiated by individuals directed at identifying a neglected opportunity (Foss et al., 2013) it is implied that entrepreneurial opportunities are not open to everyone. Openness creates the potential for bringing together and connecting actors with varying intentions and means of contributing. Connectivity enables entrepreneurs to share ideas and information in the hope of some form of mutual exchange. Connectivity represents the quality of interactions: therefore, the higher the connectivity, the better, because, without connectivity, “nothing can proceed from something else” (Hernes, 2007). Thus, connectivity in essence refers to collaboration or linkages that entrepreneurs have with other entities. In terms of connectivity, the very act of perspective-taking signals a degree of openness to new ideas and influences because the perspective taker wishes to understand how situations appear from a different point of view. The visibility created through the revelation of entrepreneurial intentions would assert interested entrepreneurs to converge and interact. While there is a substantial body of research that explores the relationship between entrepreneurial openness and opportunity recognition, there is still a gap in the literature when it comes to understanding the specific mediating roles of entrepreneurial connectivity, visibility, and creativity.

In this research, we study “Entrepreneurial openness and opportunity recognition: The mediating roles of entrepreneurial connectivity, visibility and creativity.”

LIERTAURE REVIEW

Extant entrepreneurship literature suggested that openness is a good quality for entrepreneurs to have (among other personality determinants important in entrepreneurship) (Brandstatter, 1997; Rauch & Frese, 2007b; Zhao & Seibert, 2006). Openness facilitates effective entrepreneurial behaviours in the form of connecting to others in order to facilitate business opportunities (Blanchflower & Oswald, 1998; Nair et al. 2020)

ENTREPRENEURIAL OPENNESS

Drawing from connectionism (Waldrop, 1993), we argue that surprising and sophisticated outcomes occur from the way that entrepreneurs interact each other. In our context, we define connectivity as the quality of interactions between prospective entrepreneurs. We use the quality of interaction to separate connectivity from the amount of interaction: more interaction does not necessarily mean that the interactions are of high quality which could lead to meaningful outcomes. Connectivity, therefore, entails transforming, rather than adding, to produce something new and different (Born, Frankel, & Thygesen, 2006). Connectivity represents the quality of interactions: therefore, the higher the connectivity, the better, because, without connectivity, “nothing can proceed from something else” (Hernes, 2007). However, this does not mean that all (or more) interactions are fruitful and of high quality. Not all interactions necessarily establish connectivity. The key message is that the nature and quality of such interactions lead to emergent outcomes.

Openness is a known marker for individual differences in intellectual curiosity, need for cognition, and cognitive ability (Chamorro-Premuzic & Furnham, 2005). Openness creates the potential for bringing together prospective entrepreneurs with varying intentions and means of contributing. However, for this potential to be realized, they should interact with each other, which the intervention should aim to bring about.

ENTREPRENEURIAL CONNECTIVITY

A new business requires significant knowledge about an emerging opportunity, market, product/service and associated organizational processes.

Connectivity represents the quality of interactions: therefore, the higher the connectivity, the better, because, without connectivity, “nothing can proceed from something else” (Hernes, 2007, p. 78). However, this does not mean that all (or more) interactions are fruitful and of high quality. Not all interactions necessarily

establish connectivity. The key message is that the nature and quality of such interactions lead to emergent outcomes.

ENTREPRENEURIAL VISIBILITY

The visibility created through the revelation of entrepreneurial intentions would induce interested prospective entrepreneurs to converge and interact. Studies show that high visibility triggers more cross-functional interactions (Coradi, Heinen, & Boutellier, 2015) and it implies that could increase the visibility of prospective entrepreneurs.

ENTREPRENEURIAL CREATIVITY

Entrepreneurial creativity is a widely studied topic in entrepreneurship research, as it plays a crucial role in the recognition and exploitation of new business opportunities. Baron and Tang (2011) present a comprehensive framework that sheds light on entrepreneurial creativity by considering three crucial components: the individual entrepreneur, the social context, and the entrepreneurial opportunity. The authors emphasize the importance of examining the dynamic interaction among these elements to gain insights into the emergence and cultivation of entrepreneurial creativity.

ENTREPRENEURIAL OPPORTUNITY RECOGNITION

Entrepreneurial opportunities are generally understood as “situations in which new goods, services, raw materials, and organizing methods can be introduced and sold at greater than their cost of production” (Shane and Venkataraman, 2000, p. 220). Opportunity recognition is characterized by being alert to potential business opportunities, actively searching for them, and gathering information about new ideas on products or services (Kuckertz et al, 2017)

HYPOTHESIS AND PROPOSED RESEARCH MODEL

Entrepreneurial openness as a cognitive strength that has three dimensions: engaging in learning, searching for novelty, and seeking feedback.

Openness is a known marker for **individual differences** in intellectual curiosity, need for cognition, and cognitive ability (Chamorro-Premuzic & Furnham, 2005).

Entrepreneurial openness (ENOP) as a cognitive strength that has three dimensions: engaging in learning, searching for novelty, and seeking feedback. The multidimensionality of entrepreneurial openness has been suggested in previous studies (Burmeister & Schade, 2007; Busenitz & Arthurs, 2007; Frese, 2007). **Connectivity** represents the quality of interactions: the higher the connectivity, the

better, because, without connectivity, “**nothing can proceed from something else**” (Hernes, 2007). The question that arises is “how *Entrepreneurial openness* is related to connectivity”. We argue that the more entrepreneurial openness, the more they engaged in interaction with others (see Figure 1). Therefore, it is hypothesized that:

H1a: Entrepreneurial openness is positively related to connectivity

High **visibility** triggers more interactions (Coradi, Heinzen, & Boutellier, 2015) and it implies that could **increase the visibility of entrepreneurs**.

Studies show that high visibility triggers more cross-functional interactions (Coradi, Heinzen, & Boutellier, 2015) and it implies that could increase the visibility of entrepreneurs. Therefore, it is hypothesized that:

H1b: Entrepreneurial openness is positively related to Visibility.

The discovery and development of opportunities is a key part of entrepreneurship research (Venkataraman, 1997). So, connectivity, visibility, creativity is a key characteristics of entrepreneur to converge, interact, share their scattered ideas, and search for opportunities and at that serendipitous moments opportunities emerge (Murphy, 2011; Shane, 2008).

H2a: Connectivity is positively related to entrepreneurial opportunities.

H2b: Visibility is positively related to entrepreneurial opportunities.

Entrepreneurial creativity and opportunity recognition are closely allied with person entrepreneurship fit, which indicates a business founder’s compatibility with new venture process and hence implies the likelihood of entrepreneurial success (Markman and Baron, 2003; Chaston and Sadler Smith; 2012)

H2c: Creativity is positively related to entrepreneurial opportunities.

Figure 1. Conceptual Framework

MEASUREING SCALES

ENTREPRENEURIAL OPENNESS

The multidimensionality of ENOP has been suggested in previous studies (Burmeister & Schade, 2007; Busenitz & Arthurs, 2007; Frese, 2007)

Constructs	Items	Original question	Sources
Entrepreneurial Openness (ENOP)	Learning Dimension	I follow successful entrepreneurs to learn something from them	Alenka Slavec Mateja Drnovsek, Robert D. Hisrich, (2016); Burmeister & Schade, (2007); Busenitz & Arthurs, (2007); Frese, (2007)
		I learn new marketing approaches	
		I learn new approaches about managing the business	
	Novelty Dimension	I look for ideas for new products or services	
		I look for new markets	
		I look for new business partners I search for information about introducing my firm into new geographic markets	
Feedback Dimension	I carefully examine all changes proposed to me by others (for example, I search for additional information on how to introduce changes, etc.)		
	I ask employees for their opinion on which improvements could be introduced		
	In terms of business matters, I have an open mind (thinking out of the box and evaluating all options) In business, I search for creative solutions		

ENTREPRENEURIAL CONNECTIVITY

To measure connectivity, we found the concept of high-quality connection to be relevant (Losada, 1999; Losada & Heaphy, 2004). This concept indicates relationships reflecting generativity and openness to new ideas and influences (Dutton &

Heaphy, 2003). To assess the degree of connectivity members have with each other in the organization we constructed four items to measure openness in a relationship (sample item: “We have very open relationships”) and three items to measure the degree to which a relationship is generative (sample item: “The relationships we have to enable us to generate new things”).

Constructs	Items	Original question	Sources
Entrepreneurial connectivity	Openness in a relationship	We have very open relationships	Losada, 1999; Losada & Heaphy, 2004 Dutton & Heaphy, 2003
		We are always open to listening to our coworkers’ new ideas	
		We are very open to diverse influences , even if they come from unconventional sources, such as new employees, customers, etc.	
		We are attentive to new opportunities that can make our system more efficient and effective	
	Degree to which a relationship is generative	The relationships we have enable us to generate new things	
		The relationships we have enable us to learn new things	
		The relationships we have encourage us to seek out new opportunities	

ENTREPRENEURIAL VISIBILITY OF INTENTION

This construct is not clearly defined in previous research. The visibility created through the revelation of entrepreneurial intentions would induce interested prospective entrepreneurs to converge and interact

To measure visibility of intention, through openness and connectivity, prospective entrepreneurs engage in, share ideas, and revelation of intention that promote convergence and interactions with others, hoping for a role in the opportunities and ventures emerging within.

Constructs	Items	Original question	Sources
Entrepreneurial visibility of intention	Intention	My goal is to have my own business.	Abhijeet Biswas ¹ and Rohit Kumar Verma, 2021 The Journal of entrepreneurship
		I will make every effort to start and run my own	
		I am determined to create a firm in the future	
		I have very seriously thought of starting a firm	
		I have strong intentions to start a firm someday	
		I am ready to do anything to have my own business.	

ENTREPRENEURIAL CREATIVITY

Constructs	Original question		Sources
Entrepreneurial creativity (5-point Likert)	1	I usually search out new technologies, processes, techniques and/or product ideas	Chen, M.H. and Yang, Y.J. (2009), Zhou and George (2001)
	2	I am not afraid to take risks	
	3	I usually suggest new ways to achieve goals and objectives	
	4	I often have fresh ideas	
	5	In general, I am a good source of creative ideas	

ENTREPRENEURIAL OPPORTUNITY RECOGNITION

Constructs	Original question		Sources
Entrepreneurial Opportunity	1	I am always alert to business opportunities	Kuckertz et al, 2017
	2	I am research potential markets to identify business opportunities	
	3	I look for information about new ideas on products and services	
	4	I usually scan the environment for business opportunities	

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY**RESEACH DESIGN**

This research was conducted through two stages:

1. Preliminary study for scale adjustments and
2. Quantitative survey for the research model and hypotheses test.

Table 5-1: Two main research steps and sample size

Step	Stages	Purposes	Methods	Techniques
1	Preliminary study	Scale adjustment	Qualitative n=*	Face-to-face interview
		Test Measurement scale	Quantitative n=*	Survey questionnaire using PAPI/CATI
2	Official study	Collecting data to test model and hypothesis	Quantitative n=*	

The above sample size is based on the requirements of Exploratory Factor Analysis and Multiple Regression Analysis:

Exploratory Factor Analysis (EFA): According to the research of Hair et al. (2010), for the reference of target sample size, it was suggested a minimum sample size should be five to ten times of total observed variables. In this research, the total observed variables were (*); thus, the targeted sample size should be from (*) to (*) respondents. (*): to be calculated.

Research of sample size proposed by Pallant (2005) that minimum sample size preferably should be equal or more than 150 samples.

Structural Equation Modeling (SEM): As stated by Hoelter (1983), the sample size should be equal to or more than 200 samples.

Based on and calculated by the requirements of Exploratory Factor Analysis (EFA) and Structural Equation Modeling (SEM), the sample size applied for this study was [***] (including an extra sample for data cleaning), the sample size is larger than minimum requirements to ensure data accuracy and confidence during quality control (including logic check) and data cleaning.

This research used a quantitative method with paper interviews. Respondents were screened to select the right respondents.

PRELIMINARY DISCUSSION

Entrepreneurial openness and opportunity recognition are two important concepts in entrepreneurship research. Opportunity recognition, on the other hand, refers to the process by which entrepreneurs identify and evaluate new business opportunities.

Research has shown that entrepreneurial openness can lead to better opportunity recognition. This is because entrepreneurs who are open to new ideas and experiences are more likely to identify and pursue opportunities that others might overlook. In addition, entrepreneurial openness can also help entrepreneurs to build strong networks and connections, which can further enhance their ability to identify and act on new opportunities.

The mediating roles of entrepreneurial connectivity, visibility, and creativity are also important factors to consider. Entrepreneurial connectivity refers to an entrepreneur's ability to connect with others and build a strong network of contacts. This can be especially important for identifying and accessing new opportunities.

Entrepreneurial visibility refers to an entrepreneur's ability to make themselves and their ideas known to others. The **visibility** created through the **revelation of entrepreneurial intentions** would **induce** interested entrepreneurs to **converge and interact**.

Moreover, creativity is also a key factor in opportunity recognition. Entrepreneurs who are creative and innovative are more likely to identify and pursue new business opportunities. They may also be better able to come up with unique solutions to challenges and problems they encounter along the way.

Overall, the relationship between entrepreneurial openness and opportunity recognition is complex and multifaceted. Understanding the mediating roles of entrepreneurial connectivity, visibility, and creativity can help entrepreneurs to better navigate this relationship and increase their chances of success.

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